

→ <https://conspiracychart.com/>

→ Abbie Richards Explains Conspiracies and Radicalization on TikTok | Offline Podcast

MESS 0031

MIMS 2.831: The Leftist anti-MIMS of Bunkish Propaganda, a study in POS Simpreme behavior, in allegiance to a grander POS Supreme power arch diocese of Evil.

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ABSTRACT

In this paper the author examines the deleterious effects and dark empathic personality of a POS simpreme. She has been rewarded with vast amounts of dopamine and systemic award for a behavior that borders on the psychopathic. It is, very certainly, a nescient and unscientific product that she has created (see Figure 1 below), and its chief error appears to be the use of red herrings and straw men to divide the audience. However, the mean theme of the meme appears to be a Dunning-Krugerism known as the a priori fallacy (contrast this with the author's work on the Peer Review Cult, with fact after fact with raw citation and raw data provided directly to the readership.) In the final analysis, it is revealed that her behavior is a form of "sucking up" to an establishment based around Soros/Media Matters, with a funnel of money from the ARC - Acceleration Research Consortium - whose affiliates include organizations like CTEC, TET, Khalifa Ihler Institute, GIFCT, and others; most of which are neo-liberal, pro-war, pro-censorship, and other means of controlling the political football for an established anti-free-speech agenda. The irony of being inculcated into a larger conspiracy to control data and speech, and claiming others are the conspiracy-crazed ones, should not be lost on the reader. Especially when the behavior on display is itself, so very evidently toxic and pointlessly divisive and bigoted.

Keywords: POS Theory - conspiracies - fallacies - propaganda - left-wing extremism - radicalization

Diagrammatica

Credit to **ABBIE RICHARDS** @tofology @abbiesr @abbieasr
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Explanation

Abbie¹ has made herself known to the world, proudly, as a Simpreme². As a matter of fact she is a mouthpiece for several Information Warfare outlets^{3,4}. Nevertheless, while this isn't personal, it's a fact that the above psychopathic and narcissistic conflationary behavior is *dangerous to society, and poisonous in the extreme*. Aside from enabling the POS Supremes to operate, without censure or difficulty in spreading anti-facts, anti-science⁵, and nescience, it is often turned into a means to try and dox, both personally and professionally, good common people otherwise engaged in simple freedom of speech and of belief.

The most common area of fallacy appears to be the level she has been instructed to call "Leaving Reality" where an unusual degree of Red Herrings⁶ and Straw Men⁷ are occurring. Prior to all of this, the combination of general Unearned Moral Supremacy is combined with a solid mixture of a priori fallacy⁸, anti-facts, and more red herrings. Where it goes from there is mostly into full-blown Steel Manning⁹, the means of which is a priori fallacy, loaded questions¹⁰ and answers, and a smattering of Steel+Straw manning designed to hide a smattering of factual conspiracies¹¹ among the guilt, and/or shame of "anti-semitism,"¹² which is generally very undeserved in most people.

This has to do with the organizations which the POS simp, Abbie Richards, works for, and the particular hegemonic BS they push while painting the powerless with the brush of that which they do. Some of the most ridiculous

¹ <https://twitter.com/abbieasr>

² <https://www.accresearch.org/our-team>

³ <https://www.ecotokcollective.com/our-team>

"Can TikTok Help Save The Planet? We Think So. That's Why EcoTok Exists.

EcoTok is a collective of environmental educators and activists who use TikTok as a platform for good. We celebrate diversity both in our identities and in our approaches to climate action. Among our ranks, you'll find scientists, students, activists, environmental educators, and civil servants. Our mission is one of education and inspiration, and we hope we live up to it each and every day. We came together in summer 2020 to start the next generation of education and activism after our founders Abbie Richards, Alaina Wood, Alex Silva, and Sabrina Pare came up with the idea and brought us all together (in the form of an Instagram group message, in true Gen Z fashion)."

There is literally no possible way for TikTok to save the planet. The levels of delusion within this group is pretty breathtaking. It's fine to celebrate diversity and youthful engagement, and action. **But where's the money really coming from?** Purely Trashademia... or bigger fish?

⁴ Media Matters is one of the biggest POS Supreme outlets, relating back to the king POS, George Soros himself.

<https://www.mediamatters.org/tiktok/pro-russia-propaganda-campaign-using-over-180-tiktok-influencers-promote-invasion-ukraine>

⁵ "She graduated from Colorado College with a degree in environmental science and as of August 2020 was studying for a masters in climate studies at Wageningen University & Research in the Netherlands."

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Abbie_Richards "Well there you go; there is no science 'climate studies'. There is meteorology and climate research. Climate studies is a euphemism for global warming activism and that means politics.

⁶ "something, especially a clue, that is or is intended to be misleading or distracting."

⁷ "1. an intentionally misrepresented proposition that is set up because it is easier to defeat than an opponent's real argument."

⁸ "The a priori fallacy exists when the arguer decides on what he wants to believe, and then asserts that reality matches that belief." <https://firmitas.org/logic-apriori.php>

Suggestion to Abbie et al.: use DuckDuckGo.com instead of only using Google-net.

⁹ Steelmanning is the practice of addressing the strongest form of "the other person's argument [(the steel man argument)], even if **it's not the one they presented**" One could say especially not the one the other side presented.

¹⁰ "A loaded question is a trick question, which presupposes at least one unverified assumption that the person being questioned is likely to disagree with." <https://effectiviology.com/loaded-question/>

¹¹

https://www.academia.edu/74466574/The_Peer_Review_Cult_cover_up_Conspiracy_Facts_the_fact_checkers_do_not_want_you_to_know_about

¹² "She is based in Melbourne, Australia and is of Jewish descent." Ibid.

Red Herrings are some of the bigger jokes about “conspiracy theorists”, and these have been often bolded and made larger as if to emphasize their importance versus the known conspiracy facts.

The greatest means of the entire propaganda piece appears to be the **a priori fallacy**, and let it be known that a number of these are at this point already leaning towards conspiracy facts, as has happened at an accelerated rate since 2018 and especially 2020. Take for example, chemtrails. Not only was the US government doing this in Operation LAC¹³ in the 1950s, but they have hosted “geoengineering” conferences¹⁴ openly since 2015. A “climate studies” major should, and probably does know this. Which means she is misbehaving.

The production of this social media diagram directly implicates an attempt to “control the narrative” around these conspiracy facts, shelter George Soros - one of the two largest POS Supremes at this time - and direct the “optics” against the common People who are complaining of abuse and mistreatment, actual racism and fascist bigotry, and away from the System which hurts everyone for the sake of an elite technocracy and oligarchy.

The oligarchy/technocracy can afford the production of this propaganda, and the common People aren’t sure where to turn for facts anymore. When they see these types of materials, the goal is to get a sizable percentage to doubt their doubts, and go back to burying their heads and trusting the system of propaganda and corporate shilling - even treason¹⁵, sedition¹⁶, and espionage¹⁷/terrorism. The rioters that are paid may or may not agree with any of these ideas from POS propagandists, but they tend to hate those that ask the questions that matter at the top, and that’s the major goal. By obfuscating the issues with red herrings at a key juncture, you hope to isolate the “theorists” who tend to only mean well, and sever the herd from those who might provide questions or answers. You also hope to make the main part of the herd, the “pack” or “mob” agree with ideas that are untenable, or frequently against all science and facts.

Examples of the Set

The following examples below are proofs related to the above diagram. Nevertheless, the main point is that the issues are not merely mistakes of ignorance. They are chosen, programmed ideas, which are done knowing the deleterious effect it will have on confused, vulnerable readers, particularly youth. Youth think of memes as education, as “a picture is worth a thousand words.” Meme culture is itself, not the danger, but the fact that so few children in urban regions, “blue regions” are taught so little about critical thinking, etc. Or if they come from well-to-do households, like Abbie, they react to the obvious shitshow with a screeching attachment to a set of answers that the author personally knows from previous experience when he shared them, are definitely **not solutions and not scientifically valid**. In that way, the author feels sorry for Abbie and the remainder of the members of EkoTok. But, their form of hubris is all too irksome to not be called out. Especially when the lying system of Lying Liars who Lie Still rewards them, like lost, abused puppies, for this POS supreme behavior.

Abbie is part of a conspiracy and doesn’t know it. The author was part of a conspiracy and rejected it. He feels remorse that she is “caught inside the Matrix.” Maybe she should swallow a red pill.

¹³ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Operation_LAC
<https://house.mo.gov/billtracking/bills161/hlrbillspdf/5803H.011.pdf>

¹⁴ <https://www.grc.org/climate-engineering-conference/2022/> and <https://www.ce-conference.org/>
<https://www.geoengineeringmonitor.org/resistance/>
<https://magnusconferences.com/climate-change/program/scientific-sessions/climate-engineering>
<https://climate.envsci.rutgers.edu/GeoMIP/2022.html>

¹⁵ Eg. General Milley

¹⁶ Eg. the Clintons and CNN: the Clinton News Network.

¹⁷ Eg. Feinstein et al.

Every statement made here could and has been backed up with hundreds of citations. Perhaps thousands.

Weasel Words	Straw Man	Steel Man	Red Herring	Loaded QnA	Apriori Fallacy	Unearned M.S.	Counter-factual
Chemtrails - used to dismiss talk about geoen지니어ing.	Area 51 - Abbie knows as little about Area 51, a real place, as anyone reading this.	Grounded in Reality - again Abbie sets herself up as an expert in these subjects, undeservedly.	Princess Diana - not only vague, but literally not a topic in CT camps.	Bohemian Grove - this is placed here, most perfectly. Questioning real facts leads to loss of reality.	Speculation Line - there is no place speculation starts or ends in freedom.	Science Denial - why people with liberal degrees or "studies" feel more knowledgeable about science is? DK? Confirm. Bias?	UFOs - The US Navy has said they are a fact; why is Abbie doubting they do?
"Antisemitic" PoNR - almost nothing in the chart is specifically related to Judaism .	The Beatles Never existed - literally no one ever said this in politics.	Anti-maskers/vaxxers - this is a moral assumption from misplaced superiority.	JFK Assassination - again this is a real event, what is she distracting from?	MKUltra - again, apparently questioning REALITY is a problem for Abbie.	Epstein - well he didn't kill himself, and this is seen by an examination of facts.	#FreeBrittney - again, asking a foreign country not to enforce its laws... pretty odd.	Denver Airport - again, its designs are factually symbolic and Satanic.
Antifa starting Wildfires - Well they were starting actual riot fires; pure obfuscation.	Aliens built Stonehenge - most of the altstream doesn't think this & the use of 'aliens' is obfuscation.	Essential oils - no one in CT camps thinks this, it's a pure steel man to suggest it.	Marilyn Monroe - same as JFK... this is an issue about the mob.	Roswell - This is a subject with lots of social implications that all imply "you're crazy."	Jet fuel vs. steel beams - this is a fact, but we also know Abbie knows nothing about engineering.	CRYPTIDS - Abbie continuously assumes she is a better person than others who seek answers to mysteries.	COVID-19 made in a lab; it was literally made in Wuhan's labs, this isn't a matter of opinion.
Satanic Cult Panic - phrased as if there is nothing in Satanic cults worth panicking about? Human sacrifice is evil!	Dinosaurs don't exist - who said they didn't? Again, made up by boogeymen in the conspiracy theorist camp.	Subliminal Messages - another attempt to make CT camps seem completely insane.	Avril Lav... again who cares?? Elvis Lives - no one but weird Elvis fans thinks this.	Global Warming - again climate change isn't caused by carbon, but is a fact of history and nature; loaded EVERYTHING	5G - nothing else is said here, so apparently, Abbie is unclear as to the theory.	Soy boys - seems a dig at the "inferior" Proud Boys; apparently gynecomastia is unimportant.	Government made diseases - this is also a fact; see: Fearless Johnny/Project SHAD.
Sandy Hook "Fake" - false flags are not fake, they are horrific realities.	"Vaxxers" - a pejorative; in other words a simple ad hominem with lack of argument.	Flat Earth - again, the assumption being that only CT "pyramidiots" question the globe; or that all altstream do.	Crop Circles - these are real things, but again completely off topic of CT; some are definitely manmade.	Holocaust Denial - you aren't allowed to even ask why "6 million" is a number since 1850...	Moon Landing Faked - does Abbie really know the theory well enough to say NOTHING was faked?	White Genocide - anti-whiteism and the Great Replacement are UN and corporate policy,	Obama Birth Certificate- is fake , as confirmed by separate digital forensics experts.
Follow the White Rabbit - vague reference to "the Matrix"?	Illuminati - again Abbie doesn't know what this means, and presumes easy victory.	Sandy Hook-there are many who use the deaths of children, those who do for silencing others = POS	Alien Abductions - again this isn't a CT. Abbie must have watched too many X-files episodes.	QANON - it is telling that Abbie has made this the largest on the map; she is afraid of the pedogate.	Hollow Earth - no one has been to or measured its center.	It seems the goal of this is to say if you question such blatant racism, then you are a white supremacist.	Sandy Hook- the false flag aspect of SH is not really in question; he couldn't carry the ammo by himself.
WayFair - human trafficking is a serious problem = fact; people searching out odd patterns...	Adrenochrome - here the horrors of the Human Flesh Industry are ignored.	Antifa perpetrated Capitol Insurrection - a double SM; antifa was there, and it wasn't an insurrection	Loch Ness Monster & Bigfoot - apparently an attempt to take up space with cultural phenomenon.	Both of these last two issues are complex, and have a lot of loaded social implications.	PizzaGate - again Abbie doesn't know the full discussion.	But it's a very specious argument, at best. If you look up gay or black pride, you find positives.	Soros & Bill Gates - these men are, factually, conspiring to kill people and topple the West.
... is how the DHS/DoJ find criminals; M.M.&O.!	Detached from Reality - as if she is grounded in it.		Nazis, Finland, and Elders of Zion... wtf is she talking about?	The point of putting them on the map is to make one an outcast.	NWO& DeepSt- again she is unqualified and out of her depth.	But if you look up white pride, it's always defined as racist.	

Bear in mind...

The Holocaust is real, and was not a false flag. However, asking questions as to why the number “6 million”¹⁸ is used since the early 1900s¹⁹, is not anti-semitism²⁰. It’s a matter of understanding History²¹, and nothing more. There *are* anti-semites in the alt-right; the author knows one or two. But the inquiry into history is not automatic, especially when the people that ask (for example anarcho-Libertarians) are obviously anti-Nazi or even anti-Germanic philosophy (such as the author).

The general painting of half the population as “this thing” and projecting, especially when it is so obviously done to attack patriotism and the West or America, then we must identify this type of behavior as pure POS simpreme²² behavior. We will see, as well, that these people are often infected with either unhealthy philosophies, usually hate or rage-filled (lit: screechers), or that they are physically unhealthy and unattractive, indicating an infection of the non-coded DNA²³ and the mind. Most of the infection is propaganda. Some of them, very rarely, are infected by the “black pill” itself. But as depressed as Truth makes people today, it’s not likely that the toxic conspiracy theorists are black pilling because their energy is increasing in the toxic direction (getting black or blue eyes, not sleeping enough, putting out bad programming across social media, etc.). But those that are definitely “blue pilling” are excessively aggressive and toxic, and they do try to actively infect society (like Abbie Richards does), with their nescience and hatred of the Scientific Method. The conflationary behavior this author has identified is far more dangerous than the self-isolation of an “alien reptile conspiracy theorist” to whom no one listens to. She has over 5 million lemmings following her, learning to be simpremes and become powerless to the fascist groupthink/Big Brother or “right think” power structure. It’s sad, and parasitic. However, it is what is in vogue in 2020+ for a little girl that knows essentially nothing²⁴, to go around and inflict her ignorance of topics upon the world. She’s never even known a world before the Patriot Act, when you could pick up your loved ones at the airport terminal. She’s never even known free speech. It isn’t that she has nothing to teach us. By contrast, we can see exactly what she should teach us: how **not to become a POS simpreme**.

¹⁸ <https://www.minds.com/ZUGZWANG1939/blog/246-newspaper-articles-about-6-000-000-jews-from-1900-1945-1037772629545177088>

¹⁹ <https://archive.org/details/6-million-jews-newspapers>

²⁰ <https://www.timesofisrael.com/ny-rabbi-not-even-1-million-jews-killed-in-holocaust/>

²¹ <https://forum.codoh.com/viewtopic.php?t=112>

²² “Why did you choose Tiktok to express your thoughts? Because TikTok is the best! “ <https://www.webworm.co/p/i-talk-to-the-creator-of-the-conspiracy>
This author: Yes... Chinese propaganda resources that empower a regime that ethnically cleanses Tibetans and Uighars is “the best”.

²³ https://www.academia.edu/87140767/MIMS_4_31_4_36_The_Storage_of_Karma_and_Junk_DNA

²⁴ “Do you have people in your own life who’ve fallen into any of this stuff? Like have you had to face this in person, or are you just observing this all from a distance? I remember having a very heated debate with my father in April about whether or not COVID was created in a lab.

As much as I pointed out that his rejection of scientific consensus was harmful in that it distracted from actual issues and instilled feelings of distrust, I couldn’t get him to let go of the idea. I was furious with him. He has always been an extremely logical and intelligent person. Now he denies that he ever believed the theory. I think he’s embarrassed ever since ~~they explained that the molecular structure of COVID ruled out the possibility it was made in a lab.~~ Let me be clear, my dad is not a conspiracy theorist by any means. He’s hyperrational and very emotionally intelligent. But I think that the fact that someone like him could fall prey to one of these ideas is what alerted me to the gravity of the situation.” (striktthrough added, since that never actually happened).

Author: What she’s advertising here is a) incredible ignorance of pathology, historical and documented facts, and also b) a willingness to talk down to her obviously more worldly, and well versed father, and to pretend to know more than a man of his station in life. It’s a clear problem with Millenials, especially, and this comes from their reliance upon the propaganda shitshow of the mainstream and social media for education, without the ability to do basic research. The author exposed this type of ignorance with a millennial in a debate on Climate Change: [DEBATE: Liberal Cluck Vs RamonC - Moderated By Drunk Dronetek](#)

Conclusion

There is little hope that POS simps will stop asking the system, asking the sources of money and lies, to stop funneling their fakery and lies, and demanding to worship and obey false gods and prophets. But it seems that the general public has never been more interested, or receptive, to the Truth, since widely available data and citations exist to verify this data. Numbers for the mainstream media outlets, especially the ones most associated with anti-American, anti-Presidential, and anti-factual fervor are seeing the lowest ratings and approval (as measured by trust) in their histories. Meanwhile, the youth is asking more and more questions, and parents and communities are standing up against propaganda in schools, particularly anti-white racism, history lies, and sexualization of the young and vulnerable. These brave efforts have been met with by anything from total lies and propaganda to Deep State persecution, labeling parents as terrorists. Defunding the police, closing churches (while keeping open big-box and liquor stores), and other behaviors have convinced the public of the bad faith of leaders that use fear to cajole for fascist power. Tampered elections in 2020 and 2022, as well as the bad actions of the Biden family, and the dementia of the 46th President have created a crisis in faith in the Republic as we know it.

Fortunately, for every POS there are 100 of us that stand strong against propaganda, lies, and deception. The actions of tiny liars, and their masters at the top - despite all the billions and all the leverage - cannot win in the end against the Truth. Know the Truth and it will set you free. Know history, or be doomed to repeat it. Know your enemy, or be controlled and dominated by them. Know your limits, or others will point them out for you.

Are You Paying Attention Yet?

Final Thought

Anyone willing to talk trash about their father in a public forum, despite displaying egregious levels of lack of self-awareness and massive nescience, is a serious narcissistic POS. The fact that we have built a social media system that rewards this behavior with dopamine hits, which get kids addicted and harms (especially TikTok and especially teenage girls, probably the nice ones who are good little girls) their psyches, is not an insignificant factor in the POS Wave²⁵ development. The author suggests to Congress to consider the TikTok app as an asymmetric war tool, and it's clear that the entire platform and its ability to spread nescience and hateful bigotry as is shown in this fake-ass-map made by a Media Matters shill... needs to be considered as part of a form of Cognitive Warfare²⁶ invasion campaign.

²⁵ [MESS0006: POS Theory Grows Because Agenda](#)

²⁶ <https://www.carnegiecouncil.org/media/series/asia/20190211-china-cognitive-warfare-rachael-burton>
<https://project2049.net/2019/02/12/chinas-cognitive-warfare/>
<https://www.innovationhub-act.org/sites/default/files/2021-03/Cognitive%20Warfare.pdf>

References

1. "The Conspiracy Chart: Detached From Reality," A. Richards, 2021, <https://conspiracychart.com/>
2. "Abbie Richards Explains Conspiracies and Radicalization on TikTok | Offline Podcast," Youtube/Pod Save America, youtube.com/watch?v=PB_NT1PvrJg
3. "Abbie Richards," Twitter, <https://twitter.com/abbieasr>
4. "Arc," Steering Committee, <https://www.accresearch.org/our-team>
5. "The Environmentalists of TikTok," Ecotok Collective, Our Team: 2020, <www.ecotokcollective.com/our-team>
6. "A pro-Russia propaganda campaign is using over 180 TikTok influencers to promote the invasion of Ukraine," Media Matters for America, A. Richards, 2022, <https://www.mediamatters.org/tiktok/pro-russia-propaganda-campaign-using-over-180-tiktok-influencers-promote-invasion-ukraine>
7. "Abbie Richards," Wikipedia, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Abbie_Richards
8. "Logical fallacy: A Priori," Firmitas.org, Z. Smith, 2011-2019, <https://firmitas.org/logic-apriori.php>
9. "Loaded Questions: What They Are and How to Respond to Them," Effectiviology.com, 2022, <https://effectiviology.com/loaded-question/>
10. "The Peer Review Cult "cover-up": Conspiracy Facts the 'fact-checkers' do not want you to know about," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2022, https://www.academia.edu/74466574/The_Peer_Review_Cult_cover_up_Conspiracy_Facts_the_fact_checkers_do_not_want_you_to_know_about
11. Operation LAC, Wikipedia, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Operation_LAC
12. "House Resolution No. 58," 98th General Assembly, Introduced by Rep Smith, Chief Clerk: D.A. Crumbliss. https://house.mo.gov/billtracking/bills161/hlrbillspdf/5803_H.011.pdf
13. "Processes and Impacts of Radiation Management Approaches to Climate Change," Climate Engineering Gordon Research Conference, Chairs: D. MacMartin & T. Storelvmo, Vice Chair: S. Tilmes, 2022, <https://www.grc.org/climate-engineering-conference/2022/>
14. "Resistance to Geoengineering: A Timeline," Geoengineering Monitor, <https://www.geoengineeringmonitor.org/resistance/>
15. "Climate Engineering," EGCCC 2023, magnusconferences.com, <https://magnusconferences.com/climate-change/program/scientific-sessions/climate-engineering>
16. "Twelfth GeoMIP Workshop." Gordon Conference on Climate Engineering, Workshop Organizers: A. Robock (Rutgers University) & D. Vioni (Cornell University), 2022, <https://climate.envsci.rutgers.edu/GeoMIP/2022.html>
17. "246 Newspaper Articles about 6,000,000 Jews from 1900–1945," Minds.com, Zugzwang, 2019, <https://www.minds.com/ZUGZWANG1939/blog/246-newspaper-articles-about-6-000-000-jews-from-1900-1945-1037772629545177088>
18. "10 Newspapers dating 1915 - 1938 highlighting the "6-million-Jews" narrative."archive.org, <https://archive.org/details/6-million-jews-newspapers>
19. "NY rabbi: 'Not even 1 million' Jews killed in Holocaust," The Times of Israel, R. Wootliff, 2015, <https://www.timesofisrael.com/ny-rabbi-not-even-1-million-jews-killed-in-holocaust/>
20. "Mythical '6,000,000' planned / promoted in the 1800s," The Revisionist Codoh Forum, 2022, <https://forum.codoh.com/viewtopic.php?t=112>
21. "I talk to the creator of the Conspiracy Chart," Webworm with David Farrier, D. Farrier, 2020, <https://www.webworm.co/p/i-talk-to-the-creator-of-the-conspiracy>
22. "MIMS 4.31-4.36 The Storage of Karma and Junk DNA," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2022, https://www.academia.edu/87140767/MIMS_4_31_4_36_The_Storage_of_Karma_and_Junk_DNA
23. "DEBATE: Liberal Cluck Vs RamonC - Moderated By Drunk Dronetek," Youtube, 2022, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=gGmg76nH1Eo&t=1s>
24. "MESS0006: The POS Wave continues... because ((Agenda))," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2022, https://www.academia.edu/87490521/MESS0006_The_POS_Wave_continues_because_Agenda
25. "China's Cognitive Warfare, with Rachael Burton," Carnegie Council Podcasts, 2019, <https://www.carnegiecouncil.org/media/series/asia/20190211-china-cognitive-warfare-rachael-burton>
26. "China's Cognitive Warfare," Project2049.net, R. Burton & D. Stewart, 2019, <https://project2049.net/2019/02/12/chinas-cognitive-warfare/>
27. "Social Networks: Fall 2020 Cognitive Warfare: An Attack on Truth and Thought," Innovation Hub-act.org, <https://www.innovationhub-act.org/sites/default/files/2021-03/Cognitive%20Warfare.pdf>

